

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Deliverable 8.2 (D30): Data Management Plan

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Table of contents

Executive summary	1
1. Introduction.....	2
1.1. The reason for a Data Management Plan.....	2
1.2. The Data Management Strategy	2
1.3. As open as possible, as closed as needed	3
1.4. Data management responsibilities	4
2. Types and categories of data.....	5
2.1. Statistical data from third organisations	5
2.2. Model databases.....	6
2.3. Published research results.....	7
3. Data sharing and download services	7
4. Data Management and Quality Control rules and procedures	8
5. Other research outputs, allocation of resources and data security	10
5.1. Other research outputs.....	10
5.2. Allocation of resources	10
5.3. Data security	10
6. Ethics	11
7. Acknowledgements	11
8. References.....	12
APPENDIX 1 Description of the four models and their databases used in ACT4CAP27	13

List of figures

Figure 1: Data sharing: as open as possible, as closed as needed	4
Figure 2: Architecture of the computational framework (IT-system)	8

Abbreviations / Definitions

DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable
GBD	Global Burden of Disease
GD	Green Deal
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HBS	Household Budget Surveys
SILC	Statistics on Income and Living Conditions
WR	Wageningen Research
WUR	Wageningen University & Research

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D8.2 is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the ACT4CAP27 project and is meant to convey an overall consistency of data produced and used in the scope of the project, consistent with the objectives of ACT4CAP27.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the comprehensive strategy for managing data, ensuring it adheres to the principles of being "as open as possible, as closed as needed". It details the procedures and responsibilities for data management, including the roles of the data controller and processor. The DMP summarizes the collected data, its purpose, and its relevance to the ACT4CAP27 project objectives. It also covers additional outputs generated by the project, such as publications and tools. The plan provides guidance on ensuring data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR). Additionally, the DMP specifies the resources allocated for data management, including personnel, infrastructure and funding. It explains the measures in place to ensure data security and discusses ethical considerations, including compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

This DMP will be regularly updated and will include detailed DMP's of project partners for which this is deemed necessary. The updated D8.2 will therefore include a template to offer guidance and assure compliance with the rules and procedures. This template will be set up by the project coordinator. All consortium partners actively engage and adhere to the DMP.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The reason for a Data Management Plan

Advancing analytical capacity, tools and models to support evidence-based EU agricultural policies post 2027 is at the core of the ACT4CAP27 research and modelling activities. The project applies a food system approach that ensures analytical capacity is built up to support quantitative assessments of the impacts of future agrifood policies on economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of EU's food system. The models currently used to evaluate agrifood (related) policies, including those part of EU's Green Deal (GD), have their limitations: they often focus on the primary agricultural sector and little on the food supply chain, and lack depth and scope to analyse key elements of the GD such as the reduction of input use, incentives for innovation and circular economy, and policy impacts on consumer behaviour and public health.

With regard to model improvements for policy impact assessment, four purposes of the data collection in ACT4CAP27 can be distinguished: Firstly, to expand and enhance the usage of input use, farm, food supply chain and food consumption statistics and geo-spatial information to improve the empirical validity of the model parametrization and to strengthen the representation of agrifood systems in existing models. Secondly, to develop novel dataset modules in the field of economic, social (including health), environmental and climate sustainability covering input use, sustainability indicators, and policies. Thirdly, to enhance existing models with new features enhancing the coverage of economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of food systems based on these dataset modules. And fourthly, to establish new linkages among models.

1.2. The Data Management Strategy

The data management strategy of ACT4CAP27 conforms with the FAIR standards for data, within the limitations set by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regulations (EUR-Lex, 2016). In this DMP, we describe the general guidelines to be implemented. We refer to the WUR data policy and research data management (Wageningen University and Research, 2023, p.1) to describe the following definitions. "Research data refers to any source or information generated and collected to reproduce results and conclusions of research. This definition results in a wide variety of these sources or information, including video, audio, processing and (statistical) analysis scripts, tabular data, text, interviews, photos / images, etc. Research data management concerns the correct handling, storing, preservation, sharing and legal care of research data using the FAIR principles as guidance. It covers a wide array of activities within the research data life cycle, including amongst others planning for data management, organising and structuring data, documenting data and storing/archiving/publishing data. The goal of research data management is ensuring that data is available for a long period, that data is understandable and self-descriptive (so that others can reuse it), that data follows an organised structure and that data can be shared when possible. It is important that research data are well-organised and cared for during the research project to prevent data becoming unfindable, unusable or even lost. Additionally, because data often have a longer lifespan than the research project that generates them. Researchers may continue to work on data after funding has ceased, follow-up projects may analyse or add to the data and data may be reused by other researchers. Without proper care of research data, it may become unusable or even lost to others or the partners in the future."

Focus in this DMP is on research data which will be digitally accessible. This plan provides a common ground and serves as a basis for the partners to comply to the data management strategy of the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe project. The standard questions from the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template (Enspire Science, 2021) are answered in this DMP.

1.3. As open as possible, as closed as needed

The ACT4CAP27 project uses as much publicly available data as possible. When the project uses data that fall under the privacy regulations, such as the EU household budget surveys, the project protects the data well with legal contracts with the EC and Eurostat that guarantee privacy and confidentiality. The project does not use data that can be traced back to an individual person or company.

Below we show a step-by-step plan on how to implement the principle "as open as possible, as closed as needed":

Data sharing at WUR: As open as possible, as closed as needed

Figure 1: Data sharing: as open as possible, as closed as needed

1.4. Data management responsibilities

In general, each Work Package leader is responsible for the data sets that are used for research within the project. The responsibility of the WP lead can be delegated to the Task leader or researcher responsible for data collection and/or processing. The project management team is available for support. Any changes in this responsibility can be listed in the DMP per research activity. Any delegations from the WP leaders should be notified in a written way to the project management team.

Additionally each Work Package leader:

- Supervises storage solutions and software, that match the classification of the data that are used.
- Is responsible for the correct authorisation of people for read/write access to the data (folders and/or files) and checks periodically these authorisations.
- When applicable, ensures careful handling any sensitive (e.g. confidential) data during and after the research project, (according to the data management plan).
- Is responsible for the exchange of data with the Accelerator platform, the cyberinfrastructure to support policy decision making, models integration and development, and contribute to dissemination of project results, which is built, managed and maintained under the responsibility of IIASA (the ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal, WP4).
- Ensures that all data produced and/or processed under ACT4CAP27, with the exception of that which was agreed to be permanently deleted at the conclusion of the project, is archived in a WR storage solution that meets the data classification standards.
- With the exception of that which was agreed to be permanently deleted at the conclusion of the project, archives data underlying (a) publication(s) after the research project for at least 10 years.
- Archives or deletes data according to the agreements made with clients and legal requirements.
- Registers published data sets in Pure via data@wur.nl if applicable.

2. TYPES AND CATEGORIES OF DATA

The project collects and uses publicly available international and national (at EU Member State level) data and datasets that are related to socioeconomic (including health), environmental and climate change goals and their drivers in an integrated way. Data collection is mainly part of WP2 activities that develop an indicator toolbox of health, environmental, social, and economic assessment modules based on the extended versions of the existing models in this project (WP3). In further developing these modules, data will be added to the already existing datasets the models make use of.

In general, 3 types of data will be used in ACT4CAP27: 1) statistical data, 2) model databases and 3) published research results. These datasets will be used for econometric or comparable types of analyses, as well as for the parameterisation of simulation models. All new ACT4CAP27 datasets will be collected and documented in accordance with the standards and research methodologies of institutional procedures, within EU regulations.

2.1. Statistical data from third organisations

ACT4CAP27 makes use of available agricultural and general economic statistics at sub-national level, published by authorised organisations such as Eurostat and FAO. Although they can be based on individual data, identification of individual data is usually made impossible

by the applied aggregation procedure, which for instance ensures a minimum number of individuals included in each reported category.

These data can be downloaded in the form of data tables in plain text format. Since it concerns data, which have already been published, there are no further restrictions for re-use, except for referring to the original source of the data re-used.

With regard to expanding datasets and/or creating additional data modules, different sources of statistical data will be collected and processed within the project. Examples are:

- The health assessment module will include data and analysis components on nutrition and diet-related mortality. Eurostat and national statistic bureaus will be main sources to feed this module with, for instance, food intake data. Data about health risks assessments are derived from epidemiological cohort studies and the module uses mortality projections from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD).
- Eurostat data from household budgets surveys on e.g. income, income inequality, employment, food purchases and consumption patterns (EUROSTAT SILC & HBS surveys). Next to data at national level, the project aims to benefit from EU NUTS2 level demographic, labour and population projections using data from the latest EU subnational population projections (EUROPOP2019) and other sources.
- EU and global datasets (such as FAOSTAT, UNFCCC, EDGAR, US EPA, and other national GHG inventories) to feed into the environmental impact assessment module, in particular data on GHGs, air pollution, land use intensity/biodiversity and water pollution.
- Global (e.g. GTAP¹ and OECD) and EU (Eurostat and national) data on trade and value chain performances (e.g value added and employment in processing) will be used to further validate empirically the (input-output) international value chain relations.

2.2. Model databases

In addition to the mentioned statistical datasets, ACT4CAP27 also makes use of databases of simulation models available in the consortium. These model databases are generated themselves from statistical or other model databases.

ACT4CAP27 partners are hosting and key contributors to scientifically underpinned models that are currently used at the EC for agricultural, environmental and climate policy impact assessments. Several key models are explicitly included in ACT4CAP27 to cover EU agriculture in a global context. Among those are the partial equilibrium agricultural models: CAPRI (EuroCARE, Thünen, UniBonn, SLU, UPM), AGMEMOD (Thünen, WR, PNU), GLOBIOM (IIASA) and the bioeconomy focused economy-wide general equilibrium model MAGNET (WR, Thünen)². Most of these models are also key components of the JRC iMAP modelling platform to support DG AGRI and other DGs, such as CAPRI, AGMEMOD and MAGNET. National policy makers are also using these models in a large number of EU countries. A more detailed description of these four models and their databases used in ACT4CAP is provided in Annex 1.

ACT4CAP7 will also further develop the dynamic spatial microsimulation model (simFNS) at the household level, the development of which has been initiated in BrightSpace, to shed light

¹ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/default.asp>

² <https://www.magnet-model.eu/>

on inequality and distributional issues. The model includes an elaborated health module to cover nutritional adequacy and diet-related mortality indicators. The household data (on expenditure, budget heights and weights surveys) used in this model are microdata from Eurostat. These are obtained through a formal request to the ESTAT Microdata Access Team and processed and made public (in model results) in accordance with the procedures and arrangements agreed with ESTAT.

2.3. Published research results

ACT4CAP27 builds on existing project results. The project draws on and links to activities in recent research projects that take place in international, European and national research programmes and initiatives in which consortium members are/were involved such as: SUPREMA (H2020), the iMAP model platform of JRC, FLINT (FP7), AgMIP - The Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project, MIND STEP (H2020), MEF4CAP (H2020), SUSFANS (H2020), SIM4NEXUS (H2020), MACSUR Science-Policy Knowledge Forum (MACSUR SciPol), LandSense (H2020), PEGASUS (H2020), BIOCLIMA (DG ENV), EUCLIMIT (DG Climate action), SUSDIET (SUSFOOD EraNET – FP7), LAMASUS (HEU), FOODCOST (HEU) and BRIGHTSPACE (HEU).

3. DATA SHARING AND DOWNLOAD SERVICES

ACT4CAP27 aims to make tools, data and output fully open access, following the Horizon Europe principles of Open Science to scientific publications and data. Permitting certain licenses to software (e.g. commercial solvers) and data (e.g. commercial datasets or confidential micro-data), code of models and tools will be accessible through code repositories (e.g. GitHub and GitLab) and data will be published on open data repositories (e.g. Zenodo).

The way data is shared and download services are provided is the core of the WP4 activities of the project.

In WP4, the ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal, also known as Accelerator platform, will provide an efficient cyberinfrastructure to support policy decision making, models integration and development, and contribute to dissemination of project results. The portal will be composed of Data Repositories, Model Repositories, the Computational Framework, and the Scenario Explorer. The Data Repositories will host key datasets shared across the models, used for the fundamental functioning of the models and the newly developed satellite modules based on the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and containing the various datasets produced by ACT4CAP27. We will establish data standards for model input and output, as well as for monitoring, which will be reported in a common format. Data quality and accuracy will be controlled, initially by ensuring that uploads comply with chosen exchange formats and are accompanied with complete and accurate metadata. Automated testing of the data against baselines will detect irregularities. Uploaded data will be versioned and documented, facilitating consistency checks for further analyses.

The Model Repositories will provide the models developed in ACT4CAP27 in an open access platform. The models will be hosted in dedicated GitHub/GitLab repositories, which will store the versioned models' source codes, parameter sets and their documentation. The repositories will contain wiki pages detailing the internal logic and modelling assumptions, disclosing their

influence on forecasts. The Computational Framework executes in an interlinked way runnable versions of the models and open-access modules that are connected to the Data Repositories and/or the economic models. To ensure scalability of the integrated modelling toolbox, models and modules will be modularized with formalized interfaces to facilitate data exchange and flow from the data repositories, through the modelling toolbox to the scenario exploitation in the Scenario Explorer. The Scenario Explorer infrastructure will rely on automated pipelines that will fetch and process the datasets hosted in the Data Repositories using optimised data analyses routines.

The high level architecture of the computational framework is illustrated in the graph below.

Figure 2: Architecture of the computational framework (IT-system)

4. DATA MANAGEMENT AND QUALITY CONTROL RULES AND PROCEDURES

This section focuses on processes related to data submission, validation, access, release, and query mechanisms within the Accelerator platform (whose components are described in chapter 3), ensuring adherence to FAIR data principles and robust quality control.

Data Upload and Repository

- **Data Upload:** All project-related data shall be uploaded by researchers and stakeholders to the **Accelerator** platform's data repository.
- **Stakeholder Responsibilities:** Each stakeholder will ensure the accurate submission of data, including appropriate metadata, as per the guidelines established by the Data Management Plan (DMP).

Data Validation

- **Metadata and Custom Features Validation:** After data is uploaded, it will undergo validation for compliance with metadata standards and any custom specifications defined by the project team.
- **Validation Process:** The Accelerator platform will facilitate this validation process to ensure data quality, completeness, and integrity, thus meeting the project's data standards.

Metadata Standards

- **Metadata Format:** Metadata will be structured in **JSON format**, providing a flexible and easily parsable structure for storing and exchanging data.
- **Dataset Type Standards:** The standards for metadata will be established based on the **type of dataset**, ensuring that each dataset has relevant and appropriate attributes.
- **Descriptive Metadata:** Metadata should be **descriptive enough** to facilitate quick discovery of datasets and ensure accurate descriptions. This promotes **trust** in the datasets and enhances their reusability across various contexts.

Data Release and Access

- **Data Release:** Once validated, data can be marked as "released" by an authorized user within the Accelerator platform.
 - **Public or Private Release:** Data can be released either **publicly** (open access) or **privately** (restricted access) based on permissions and the project's requirements.
- **Unique HTTP Links for Dataset Access:** Each dataset will have a unique **HTTP link** for direct access.
 - If the data is private, an **authorization token** must be presented along with the link to authenticate access, while public datasets can be accessed without such tokens.
- **Data Catalog:**
 - A dedicated **Data Catalog** will be maintained for all released datasets.
 - The catalog will provide access to metadata for all datasets, regardless of their public or private release status.
 - Public datasets will be downloadable directly from the catalog, while access to private datasets will require authentication and authorization.

Data Query and Interoperability

- **Data Querying:**

- All data within the repository will be **queryable**, allowing users to retrieve only the specific portions of the data they require.
- This selective retrieval ensures efficient use of resources and improves performance when working with large datasets.
- **Interoperability:**
 - The query mechanisms support **interoperability** with other computing tasks, enabling the data to be used across various computational workflows and platforms.
 - This ensures that the data can be seamlessly integrated into other processes, enhancing its usability for different project components.

Conclusion

This data management strategy covers the full data lifecycle, from submission and validation to access, release, and query capabilities. It ensures compliance with FAIR data principles, enhances interoperability, and strengthens the overall quality control framework for Task 8.2. By incorporating JSON metadata standards based on dataset types and emphasizing descriptive metadata, the strategy fosters trust and reusability of the project's datasets, contributing to the successful delivery of scientific and technical project objectives while ensuring secure, efficient, and responsible data handling.

5. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS, ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES AND DATA SECURITY

5.1. Other research outputs

Other outputs of the project, such as digital outputs (e.g., software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) will be monitored by the project team. Also, methodologies for stakeholder engagement, if openly accessible, can be shared through Zenodo or similar services.

5.2. Allocation of resources

As stated in the Grant Agreement, ACT4CAP27 will publish in open access journals, for which budget has been allocated. In general, each work package leader is responsible for the datasets, which are used for research within the project. This responsibility can be delegated to the task leader. The project management team is available for support. Any changes in this responsibility can be listed in the DMP, per research activity. As earlier described in this DMP, at this point in the project (M6), the installation of a data access committee does not seem necessary because the responsibilities have been assigned in the project.

5.3. Data security

As a general rule, data files are stored in locations secured by personalised username and password combinations, only accessible by authorised staff known to the respective data providers.

Within WR we apply risk management to data collection, processing and storage. All unique data sets will be classified in order to determine the underlying risks and based on the

integrity, availability and confidentiality of the data itself. An appropriate tool will be selected to have an overview of centrally managed applications that are safe to use for WR data.

All tools used during research will also be selected on their security baseline and will be checked beforehand if the use of these tools may result in (new) unidentified risks.

For the project in general, data security is in place using the project collaboration platform MS Teams, which is linked to the SharePoint site, hosted on the WR network. The used servers are frequently updated. Using Google Drive, for example, is not allowed, due to the risk of security holes and loss of control over the data.

6. ETHICS

The most relevant ethical risk for ACT4CAP27 is the potential mis-use of research findings, namely originating from potential re-identification of individuals. When processing personal data, the consortium will comply with the GDPR principles. This means that, when the data cannot be anonymized fully, in the development of the project, Article 5(1) of the GDPR, enshrining the principles of personal data protection, will be considered. The project does not foresee the use of individual and/or personal data, and will make use of publicly available data. In case data is not public, such as Eurostat household budget survey data, access to it will follow the official procedures for a data access request (in case of the Eurostat household budget data a request will be submitted to the ESTAT Microdata Access Team, to be contacted through ESTAT-Microdata-access@ec.europa.eu).

ACT4CAP27 will co-develop a Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform with stakeholder engagement to efficiently connect data with models and end users with modelers, fostering a continuous exchange through this platform. For this, we will map and engage stakeholder groups via a series of events and activities, where they will provide input to the various components of the project. Involvement of stakeholders and the linked feedback and participatory **processes** are very important within this project. This includes aspects where ethical and gender issues must be checked (e.g. the selection of stakeholders, their consent for participation in the meetings, data privacy and protection). In line with the ethics self-assessment, actions will be executed for involvement of humans and for the protection of personal data. The GDPR has been analysed and reviewed in order to align the project objectives accordingly. All partners should have their internal procedures updated and are compliant with current legislation. To be sure that partners comply, a compliance check may be organised asking the partners to confirm compliance. Consent forms will be provided and shall include information on which e-mail to contact to access, rectify, delete and/or retract data. In the case of consent being rescinded, the processing of the user's data is to stop immediately. The retraction of consent should be completed as easy as consent was acquired.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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APPENDIX 1 DESCRIPTION OF THE FOUR MODELS AND THEIR DATABASES USED IN ACT4CAP27

GLOBIOM

The Global Biosphere Management Model (GLOBIOM) has been developed and used by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) since the late 2000s. It is a partial-equilibrium model that represents various land use-based activities, including the agriculture, forestry, and bioenergy sectors. The model is built following a bottom-up setting based on detailed grid-cell information, providing the biophysical and technical cost information. This detailed structure allows a rich set of environmental parameters to be accounted for. Its spatial equilibrium modelling approach represents bilateral trade based on cost competitiveness.

GLOBIOM takes land use inputs for the agriculture, livestock, forestry, and bioenergy sectors from FAOSTAT and the Spatial Production Allocation Model (SPAM). SPAM data is processed with aid of the `mapspam2globiom` R package⁵. In the case of the EU, crops are allocated across NUTS2 regions using data from EUROSTAT. Harvested areas are based on FAOSTAT statistics but spatially allocated using data from the SPAM. Yields for all locations and crops are determined in a geographically explicit framework by the Environmental Policy Integrated Climate Model (EPIC). The yields are distinguished by crop management system and land characteristics by spatial unit.

Total forest area in GLOBIOM is calibrated according to FAO Global Forest Resources Assessments (FRA). The available woody biomass resources are provided by the forest model G4M for each forest area unit and are presented by mean annual increments that are divided into commercial roundwood, non-commercial roundwood and harvest losses, thereby covering the main sources of woody biomass supply.

The model is primarily implemented in GAMS. Prior to running GLOBIOM, EPIC and G4M are run, and a pre-compilation stage converts raw input data into GAMS-ready data that serves as input for the model and scenario stages. This includes GDX, GMS data-definition, and CSV files.

On conclusion of the scenario runs, output data for the various scenarios is collected and merged. Through stages of filtering and aggregation, the output data is distributed across a series of GAMS parameters that are the representational near equivalent of Python/R data frames as well as a series of supportive set definitions. Parameters and sets are all included into a single output GDX. Data dimensions include a spatial specifier for the various grid cells countries, or regions; indicator; unit; item; scenario indices; and time. Interfaces primarily access these output parameters and sets.

To interface GLOBIOM to R, the `gdrrw` R package is used in the tidyverse R framework. `globiomvis` R package⁶. It allows GDX content to be explored, read, and written. Read GDX data is represented as R data frames which are readily converted into the modernized data frame representation called tibble that is at the core of the tidyverse. The tidyverse is a coherent and lucidly designed set of R packages that cover various aspects of data analysis such as tidying, transformation, manipulation, and declarative visualization. On top of `gdrrw` and the tidyverse, a GLOBIOM visualization interface is provided by the `globiomvis` package⁸. It supports analysis and generation of a variety of scenario plots. In addition, `globiomvis` enables creation of maps for the various regionally and spatially explicit representations of the model.

For interactive exploration—and intended primarily for training and outreach purposes—a graphical user interface (GIO) based on GGIG (Britz, 2014) is available as an alternative way of performing analysis, visualization, and parameterizing and running the core version of the model.^{9 10} GGIG is Java-based and orchestrates numerous Java libraries that provide rich visualization and analytical functionality. GGIG is specialized to GLOBIOM purposes via a hierarchy of XML configuration files. To compensate for their fragility, these XML configuration files are validated against and further documented (beyond the reach of the regular GGIG documentation) through annotated XSD schema files. To ease maintenance and updates of the GUI, the XML files are to a large degree generated from the GLOBIOM code base as well as from the GGIG state persistence INI file by means of Python scripts.

CAPRI

The CAPRI agricultural economic model has been developed since 1999 with the help of several EU research projects. The model supports the policy-making process by means of quantitative analyses of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) at global and regional levels. The aim is to estimate in advance the impact of agricultural policy decisions on production, income, trade, and the environment using the model. To guarantee comparability of results between member countries and over time, CAPRI uses standardized and harmonized data sources from EUROSTAT, the EU Commission and the FAO or OECD, as far as possible. A large part of the development is devoted to data preparation or standardization to reference units that are thus comparable over time and across regions in Europe. The database consolidation steps are designed in such a way that all data changes can be repeated so that newly available data sets or improved statistics can be integrated without problems. Such a concept allows the data consolidation to evolve continuously without having to accept methodological breaks. This means a high level of hardware requirements and methodological competence. For example, the creation of the database requires the computing power of a high-performance computer for about one day, although many of the processes run in parallel. The result of the database consolidation steps are time series for the agricultural sector at the regional Nuts2 level for the topics of agricultural accounts (EAA), land use, animal stocking density, factor income, prices, market balance, nutrient requirements, and nutrient suppliers. In addition, the dataset contains a consistent representation of regional feed requirements and feed resources. Special features are, apart from the balancing consistency framework, the bundling across regions (Nuts2, Nuts1, MS, EU) and the detailed environmental indicators in greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient balancing. An additional gain is the accompanying archiving of European datasets, as it is not uncommon for statistics to become unavailable after a few years. As experience shows, the dataset has a high usefulness for many analyses and projects, especially in the European context, although better-resolved data sources are sometimes available at regional or national level. The generation of consistent time series is part of the data work. The time series are also used to derive trends for future development and to create reference points for the future. These future projections, often referred to as baselines, use official agricultural projections from the EU Commission in addition to trend projections from the time series. The rule here is that the regional trends in the sum of all regions should reflect the projection of the EU Commission. These projections have a projection period of about 10 years and serve as a reference data set in many European analyses in the agricultural and environmental sector. In recent years, long-term projections with reference to climate development have also been produced. Here, external projections to the SSPs from the GLOBIOM and PRIMES models are used. Data consolidation uses statistical or mathematical estimation methods with the goal of adjusting the values of the statistics only when economic and bio-physical relationships or other statistics require it. If, for example, the yield multiplied by

the area does not correspond to the production volume from the statistics, the yield is adjusted accordingly. The original data and the new estimated data are stored together for comparisons and better tracking. A metadata model allows the necessary information on the statistics and on the processing steps to be summarized and stored efficiently. Traceability in case of changes in the routines is ensured by the version control software SVN. The network is supported by eight institutions, including 3 universities, one company and four research institutes. In addition, the EU Commission-JRC supports the network with positions and corresponding calls for proposals. For each data consolidation step in the model there are responsible developers. Many institutions support the network with personnel as well as with hardware and software infrastructures. Currently, all data is freely available and are downloadable.¹¹ The **interfaces** to access the databases are currently based on a graphical user interface GGIG (Britz, 2014).

¹² The GUI comprises a generic and powerful tool for exploitation, accessing and exporting of results. Results from the different work steps of CAPRI generated by GAMS are stored in GDX format as multi-dimensional sparse data cubes. The regional time series data base of CAPRI covers almost 15 Mio non-zeros values. To access these huge data quantities in a user-friendly and efficient way, an XML file defines views in the data. Each view is firstly characterised by a selection or filter for the different dimensions such as regions, activities, items, or scenarios. Secondly, a pivot is defined which maps the data base dimension to viewport dimensions, such as the columns or rows of a table, or the regions shown in a map. And thirdly, it defines the view type: a table, different type of graphs or a map. Fourthly, views may comprise links to other views, like the concept of hyperlinks in WEB pages, which allows a "drill-down" like exploitation from general to specific aspects, or vice versa.

But the user maintains his freedom: he may tune the view to his own needs, by adding his own selections, change the pivot or the view type. Equally, fonts, colour, cell sizes or properties of the graphs may be set by the user. His personal settings can be stored for future session. And finally, the mapping viewer allows for rather flexible classifications and colouring options. The details with examples are discussed in a chapter of the CAPRI documentation.¹³ In addition to the GGIG there exists an **interface** to import the result database of CAPRI into Excel using an COM add for Excel based on the GDX API of GAMS and the MS .net framework. After opening Excel, the COM add-is loaded and a new Ribbon "CAPRI REPORTS" can be used to import formatted result table with long texts into Excel, ready for reporting.¹⁴ Similarly, a R package interface to access the CAPRI database exists developed by Mihaly Himics. The R package reads GDX files and prepares figures and charts. ¹⁵ It includes functions for processing, visualizing, and analysing both the model databases and simulation results. It has been designed to complement (rather than to replace) already existing GIGG for CAPRI. The advantages of capriR compared to graphical User Interface options include dissemination of model-databases and simulation results, automated reporting requiring additional (post-model) calculations, creating publication-quality maps and other data visualizations. As CAPRI covers EU agricultural production activities with fine geographical detail, spatial data analysis and visualization are of a particular importance for capriR. CAPRI results are linked to commonly used spatial data packages thus enabling the user to create high-resolution static or interactive maps. With capriR you can also access rapidly the databases and simulation results of the CAPRI modelling system. The modularity of the R programming language allows for directly applying advanced econometric and statistical techniques from other (open-source) R packages on the data sets retrieved from CAPRI. Although capriR is only directly useful for the relatively small user base of CAPRI, some of the general strategies for rapid package development might be re-used for similar, large scale economic models.

MAGNET

The policy landscape is becoming increasingly complex with interrelated global challenges stretching across domains previously handled in relative isolation. An example is the Paris agreement of 2016 (UNFCCC 2016) which will have widespread repercussions for the way in which the world economy operates. Such commitments require policymakers to look at impacts beyond their own domain and decades ahead. With feedback loops abound impacts of interventions become theoretically ambiguous requiring ex-ante integrated modelling tools to explore expected impacts of policy interventions, trade-offs, and synergies across multiple domains. Such challenges are faced by MAGNET (Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool). The MAGNET model is a global general equilibrium model. MAGNET is based on the LEITAP model which has been used extensively in policy analyses. MAGNET offers more flexibility in model aggregation (definition of regions and sectors) and more options for changing a model's structure. The main aim of MAGNET is to offer a global applied general equilibrium modelling framework which can be easily tailored to specific research questions and regions and products of interest. This flexibility allows researchers to adjust the complexity of a model to the questions at hand as well as to their own level of understanding of global CGE models. The core of the MAGNET database is the GTAP database. MAGNET uses a series of additional databases, such as GTAP satellite databases, FAOSTAT (commodity balances, land use, land cover and fertilizer), data on biofuels from the International Energy Agency and land use parameters taken from the IMAGE model. On average for almost each module in MAGNET (Figure 5) additional data is included in the MAGNET-database, complemented with scenario data like projections of GDP and population. The database is constructed in several steps: the first step includes gathering raw data from the web or other sources and reshape to standard input formats by hand or using code. The next step is performed by using DSS (Figure 5). You can select the desired GTAP database, add other databases and formulate new regions, sectors, commodities, and endowments. These steps lead to the desired database for a specific project. The processing of data is for almost 100% coded to make it easier to update the original source data, to track how data are processed and to maintain flexibility using different GTAP database versions.

AGMEMOD

AGMEMOD is an econometric, dynamic, partial-equilibrium, multi-country, multi-market model that covers the main EU agri-food markets at national level. It is built as a set of commodity-specific model templates in country-specific models. This allows for combination of national markets into the EU block. The model includes: six types of cereals, three types of oilseeds and their processed products, oil and meal, sugar beet and sugar, protein crops and potatoes, live animals (cattle, pigs, sheep and goats) and meats (beef, pig meat, poultry, sheep and goat meat), raw milk and its processed products drinking milk, cream, fresh dairy products, butter, skimmed milk powder, whole milk powder and cheese, and vegetables and fruit commodities (such as tomatoes) are currently being built in.

The variables simulated for the crop sectors include market prices, area harvested, yield, total production (as a product of yield and area), total domestic use as a sum of food, feed, processing uses and losses, total import, export and change in stocks. Apart from the markets for meat and dairy products, AGMEMOD considers markets for live animals and simulates such variables as livestock herds (i.e., number of dairy cows, sows, ewes, slaughter pigs, etc.), animals crop and slaughter weight.

The agricultural sectors interact in the model on the demand and supply sides as substitutes in consumption and production. This interaction is captured by the model structure that allows for solving the AGMEMOD system for each of the projection years following the partial equilibrium approach of market clearing prices.

The endogenous variables of the model are computed with equalities and behavioural equations. For example, rapeseed oil production in AGMEMOD is computed as equality. It is a product of rapeseed use for processing and the crush coefficient. The use of rapeseed for processing is, in turn, a behavioural equation. Its parameters are econometrically estimated from the time series data. Some of the parameters of the behavioural equations in AGMEMOD rely on expert knowledge and literature.

AGMEMOD uses EUROSTAT, national statistics and expert data sources. These comprise AGMEMOD database which prior to the use for estimation of the model's equations is subject to the "balancing" process. This process implies generation of the missing observations in the series and examination for adhering to the balance principles (e.g., crop yields equal total production divided by area harvested, the sum of production, domestic use, stocks, import and export equals zero).

Thanks to the use of econometrically estimated equations, AGMEMOD does not require the classic parameter calibration process and the use of the external baseline to produce its projections. In the recent years, however, the model has been used for producing the JRC baseline at the EU countries level. Therefore, AGMEMOD projections at the EU aggregate level have been scaled to the official baseline of the European Commission, i.e., EU medium term Outlook generated by the Aglink-COSIMO model. The scaling procedure aims at bringing the values of the aggregated variables as close as possible between the two models. It follows a standardized step-wise process, which is based on adjustment of the AGMEMOD parameters. For further information, see the model's website: <https://agmemod.eu/about-agmemod/model>

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<https://act4cap27.eu>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

<http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>